

Table S1. Coordinates of the sampling sites

Sites	N	E
1	41.2370578	0.52286131
2	41.23003264	0.52787251
3	41.23036527	0.5503194
4	41.22607146	0.54463941
5	41.24626186	0.49311459
6	41.2308812	0.54732928
7	41.22925772	0.5441435
8	41.23009697	0.53918734
9	41.23101606	0.54858596
10	41.23239605	0.55102207
11	41.22930929	0.54628745
12	41.22730264	0.54630236
13	41.22830532	0.54571207

Figure S1. Description of the sampling sites (numbered stars) located nearby the chlor-alkali Factory. The map corresponds to 2014 (within the VOC sampling period) and shows the mass of half-dredged industrial residues and the action of the grab. Numbers refer to the coordinates of Table S1. Images from the Catalan Institute of Geography and Geology (ICGC). Reconeixement Internacional 4.0, CC BY 4.0 License.